

Design and Material Consideration of Screw Jack with single and double start threads

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Abstract: Power screws are used to transmit motion or power by the use of helical translator motion of the screw threads. Power screw are also called translation screws. A jack screw is a typical example of a power screw applications in which a small force applied in a horizontal plane is used to raise or lower a large load. This paper study the effect of varying type of screw and nut material's, the load to be lifted, number of start threads on the screw, helix angle, number of threads on nut outside diameter, and height of the nut, of screw jack with square thread. The significance of this work is to provide the designer with a number of choice to select a safer, convenient and reliable screw jack design. Moreover, the results show that there is a number of choice depending on job requirement which allow best suited combination selection of each screw and nut material's pair.

Keywords: power, screw, nut, efficiency, jack, thread, load, square, material,.

1.Introduction

A screw jack is an example of power screw an referred to as a mechanical device that increase of an effort force. The power screws (also known as *translation screws*) are used to convert rotary motion into *translatory* motion. For example, in the case of the lead screw of lathe, the rotary motion is available but the tool has to be advanced in the direction of the cut against the cutting resistance of the material. In case of screw jack, a small force applied in the horizontal plane is used to raise or lower a large load. Power screws are also used in vices, testing machines, presses, etc. In most of the power screws, the nut has axial motion against the resisting axial force while the screw rotates in its bearings. In most screws, the screw rotates and moves axially against the resisting force while the nut is stationary and others the nut rotates while the screw moves axially with no rotation [1,2]. The power screws generally have an efficiency of the order of 40-70 percent depending upon the helix angle of the thread and coefficient of sliding friction between the nuts and screws. However, high transmission efficiency, usually 90 percent or more, can be obtained by ball screws. The most common used forms of thread for power are: first Acame thread which is trapezoidal-shaped thread with a slight slope given to its sides which lower its efficiency and produce radial pressure on the nut. however, it increases the base area which improves its shear strength. Second A square thread

with sides perpendicular to the thread axis and with zero inclined angle which results into maximum transmission efficiency and minimum radial pressure on the nut. Third Buttress thread is useful in those applications which have to bear a large force acting along the axis in one direction only and have a nearly perpendicular thrust surface which results in low radial pressure and the transmission efficiency is approximately equivalent to that of the square thread. Forth Ball screws are a type of power screw. In power screws when two or more parallel threads are employed to increase the travel of nut per revolution, these threads are called multi-start threads. The mechanical advantage of the multi-start thread screw is smaller; however, its transmission efficiency is higher because of the increased lead angle [3].

A power screw simply consists of basically two parts (screw and nut) which entails several advantages such as: large load carrying capability, minimal number of parts, smooths, and low maintenance, relative easy to manufacture (no specialized machinery is required), self-locking capability etc. Due to the fact that power screw nut and screw mate each other with rubbing surfaces the produced friction is much higher compared to other machine elements which mate with rolling surfaces such as bearings. This is the main reason why the degree of efficiency for power screw is approximately up to 70%. The efficiency of power screw can be improved by:

- changing thread geometry, profile
- changing thread parameters for a given profile
- Increasing the helix angle
- using multi start-screws
- reducing the coefficient of drag [4]

The square thread profile is the most efficient profile [4,5].

The objective of the present work is to study the effect of varying some of the parameters that affect the design components of a jack screw. The considered independent variables are yield strengths of screw and nut materials, coefficient of friction between screw and nut, the load to be lifted, number of start threads. The dependent parameters are helix angle, jack screw efficiency, number of threads on the nut, outside diameter of the nut, major and minor or root diameter, and pitch of screw. Moreover, the considered independent and the corresponding resulted dependent variable will be used to compare different combinations of screw-nuts material's pairs.

2.Design of screw jack and nut

Fig.1 shows the various parts of screw jack

Fig1: Screw jack

2.1. Design of screw [1,3,5]

1.First of all, find the root diameter(d_c) by considering that the screw is under compression, i.e.

Allowable tensile strength, σ in N/mm^2

$$\sigma = \sigma_{y,(screw)} / FoS \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where $\sigma_{y,(screw)}$ = yield strength of the screw material , N/mm^2

FoS = factor of safety for screw material

The root diameter or minor diameter, d_c in mm

$$d_c = \sqrt{4W/(\pi\sigma)} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where W = load to be lifted , kN

According to the calculated value of the root diameter, d_c the values of the major diameter ,pitch, and the mean diameter for square thread will be selected from of a coarse series as per IS:4694-19688 [1].

2.Find the helix angle and the friction angle

The average helix angle α

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}(p/(\pi d)) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where p = pitch , mm

d =Mean diameter of the screw , mm .

$$= (d_c + d_o)/2$$

The friction angle, ϕ

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \mu \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

μ = coefficient of friction between screw and nut

Check self-locking condition $\alpha > \phi$

3.Find the torque(T_l) required to derive the screw against friction between the screw and the nut during lifting of load.

The torque required to lift the load, T_1 in $N.m$

$$T = Wd/2 = [Wd \tan(\alpha + \phi)]/2 \dots(5)$$

Assuming uniform pressure distribution between the cup and the screw head, the mean diameter of the screw head and cup assembly D_c in mm

$$D_c = 2(D_1^3 - D_2^3)/3(D_1^2 - D_2^2) \dots(6)$$

D_1 = Inner diameter of nut, mm

D_2 = Outer diameter of nut collar, mm

The fractional torque due to the collar action between the cup and the screw T_C in $kN.mm$

$$T_C = \mu_c D_c W/2 \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

The total torque required to derive the screw T_R in $kN.mm$

$$T_R = T + T_C \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

4. Stresses in screw

(i) Induced shear stress due to applied torque

$\tau_{(screw)}$ in N/mm^2

$$\tau_{(screw)} = 16T/\pi d_c^3 \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

(ii) Crippling stress σ_{cr} in N/mm^2 when the screw is at full lifted condition

$$\sigma_{cr} = W[1 + a(l/k)^2]/A \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

Where l = Lift of screw + 0.5 Height of nut, mm

a = Ranking constant

k = Radius of gyration

(iii) Bending stress

The bending moment due to the possibility of eccentric action of the applied load

$$M = W \times e \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

M = The bending moment in, $N.mm$

e = eccentricity, mm

Bending stress σ_b in N/mm^2

$$\sigma_b = 32M/(\pi d_c^3) \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

(iv) Maximum principal stress σ_{max} in N/mm^2

$$\sigma_{max} = 0.5 \left[(\sigma_{cr} + \sigma_b) + \sqrt{(\sigma_{cr} + \sigma_b)^2 + 4\tau_{(screw)}^2} \right] \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

(v) Check factor of safety, F_{sos}

$$F_{sos} = \sigma_{y,(screw)} / \sigma_{max} \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

$F_{sos} > FOS$

2.2 Design of nut

4. Find the height of nut (h) and the number of threads in contact with screw spindle n , by considering the bearing pressure on the nut.

$$N = 4W/[\pi P_b (d_o^2 - d_c^2)] \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

N = Number of threads in contact with screw spindle.

$$h = N \times p \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

h = height of nut in mm

p = Pitch of threads in mm

5. Check the shear stresses in the nut

$$\tau_{(nut)} = W/(\pi \cdot N \cdot d_o \cdot t) \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

$$t = \text{Width of thread, mm} = P/2 \dots\dots\dots(18)$$

Check $\tau_{(nut)} < \tau_{all,nut} \dots\dots\dots(19)$

$\tau_{all,nut}$ = allowable shear strength of nut material, N/mm^2

$$\tau_{all,nut} = 0.56 \sigma_{y,(nut)} \dots\dots\dots(20)$$

2.3. The design steps of screw jack are shown as flow chart of fig.2

Fig.2: Flow chart for the design of screw jack

2.4 Design considerations

In the design of screw thread, a square thread profile is considered for the screw and nut of bottle type screw jack. A C++ computer program software was used for performing calculations. In the used program it is assumed that the jack is operated by one person who can apply 400 N load, coefficient of friction $\mu=0.15$, maximum lift 200mm, lifting loads (10 to 50KN) and the bearing pressure on the nut 12 N/mm^2 . However, standard pitches (5 to 7mm), standard screw core diameters (17 to 33mm) and standard screw outside diameters (22 to 40mm) are taken in order to calculate efficiency of different screw-nut material combination. Moreover, for screw-nut material combination standard values of yield strength are taken as reference parameters Table (1). Since the screw jack is subjected to various stresses, namely compression, torsional, shear, bending, and buckling, therefore for accounting for these stresses we consider a high factor of safety, $FoS=5$.

Table 1: Materials considered in the study

component	material	Yield strength N/mm^2
screw	Nickle ₁	1200
	Steel ₁	1000
	Titanium	800
	Steel ₂	350
nut	Copper	400
	Steel ₂	350
	Magnesium	305
	Nickle ₂	110
	Phosphorus Bronze	35

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Results:

Table 2 through 8 lists the results obtained using C++ computer program software. The input data are load to be lifted, lift required, yield strength of the screw material, factor of safety, yield strength of the nut material, coefficient of friction. The output data are

namely outside diameter of the screw " d_o ", the core diameter " d_c ", the pitch " P "

diameter of nut", the number of threads on the nut " N ", efficiency of screw jack " η ", and the helix angle " α "

Table 2: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of titanium-nickel with single start threads.

Parameter \ Load KN	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	24	26
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	19	21
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	24	26	28	32	35
N "mm"	9	11	17	20	23
Efficiency η	21.2	21.2	21.2	19.8	18.6
Helix angle α	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.2	3.9

Table 3: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of steel-phosphorus bronze with single start threads.

Parameter \ Load KN	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	26	30	36	40
d_c "mm"	17	21	24	30	33
P "mm"	5	5	6	6	7
D_2 "mm"	29	37	44	52	57
N "mm"	9	10	10	12	12
Efficiency	21.2	19.2	18.6	16.5	17.2
Helix angle	4.7	4.04	3.9	3.3	3.5

Table 4: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of steel-copper with single start threads.

Parameter \ Load KN	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	22	24
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	17	19
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	22	23	24	24	27
N "mm"	9	11	17	22	25
Efficiency	21.2	21.2	21.2	21.2	19.8
Helix angle	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.2

Table 5: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of nickel-magnesium with single start threads.

Parameter	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	22	22
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	17	17
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	22	23	24	25	26
N "mm"	9	11	17	22	28
Efficiency %	21.2	21.2	21.2	21.2	21.2
Helix angle	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7

Table 6: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of nickel-magnesium with double start threads.

Parameter	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	22	22
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	17	17
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	22	23	24	25	26
N "mm"	6	11	17	22	28
Efficiency %	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9
Helix angle	9.3	9.3	9.3	9.3	9.3

Table 7: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of steel-copper with double start threads.

Parameter	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	22	22
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	17	19
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	22	23	24	24	27
N "mm"	6	11	17	22	25
Efficiency %	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	24.3
Helix angle	9.3	9.3	9.3	9.3	8.4

Table 8: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of steel-phosphorus bronze with double start threads.

Parameter	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	24	36	40
d_c "mm"	17	17	19	30	33
P "mm"	5	5	5	6	7
D_2 "mm"	29	34	40	52	58
N "mm"	6	11	11	11	11
Efficiency %	25.9	25.9	24.3	20.4	21.2
Helix angle	9.3	9.3	8.4	6.6	6.9

Table 9: Screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of titanium-nickel with double start threads.

Parameter	Load KN				
	10	20	30	40	50
d_o "mm"	22	22	22	24	26
d_c "mm"	17	17	17	19	21
P "mm"	5	5	5	5	5
D_2 "mm"	24	26	28	32	35
N "mm"	6	11	17	20	23
Efficiency %	25.8	25.9	25.9	24.3	22.9
Helix angle	9.3	9.3	9.3	8.4	7.7

3.2 Discussions:

1-By inspecting fig. (1) and fig. (2) it can be seen that the efficiency of screw jack with screw-nut materials combination of nickel -magnesium remain constant until load of 40KN and then decreases gradually. In the case of steel-bronze combination the efficiency decreases gradually until the 40kN load and then increases gradually at 50KN due to pitch changing. In the case of titanium-nickel combination the efficiency remains constant up to load of 40kN after that decreases gradually and we note that it is higher for double start threads than for single one.

Fig. 1: Applied load versus efficiency for single start threads

Fig. 2: Applied load versus efficiency for double start threads

2-From fig. (3) and fig. (4) it clear that the helix angle remains constant for the screw-nut combination of nickel-magnesium with respect to load. In the case of steel-copper combination the helix angle is also remain constant up load of 40kN and after that decreases while in the case of steel-phosphorus bronze it decreases up to load of 40kN and then increases at 50kN because of pitch change. In titanium-nickel combination case the helix angle also remain constant but up to 30kN load and then decreases and for all cases of combination the helix angle is always higher for double start than for single start threads of screw jack.

Fig. 3: Applied load versus helix angle α for single start threads

Fig. 4: Applied load versus helix angle α for double start threads

3.From fig (5) and fig (6) in general the number of threads in the nut increases with increasing the applied load for all the combinations of screw-nut except for the combination of steel-bronze where it become constant after 20kN load. The numbers of threads are generally approaching one another for double single start threads of screw jack.

Fig. 5: Applied load versus number of threads on the nut for single start threads

Fig. 6: Applied load versus number of threads on the nut for double start threads

4-From fig. (7) and fig, (8) it is clear that the outside diameter of the nut increases with increasing the applied load for all cases of considered combination of screw-nut where higher values are for steel-phosphorus bronze and lower values in decreasing order are, titanium-nickel, and then steel-copper, while nickel-magnesium combinations are approximately the same.

Fig.7: Applied load versus outside diameter of the nut for single start thread.

Fig. 8: Applied load versus outside diameter of the nut for double start threads

4. Conclusion

In the design of jack screw the efficiency is very important specially in continuous power screw applications. In screw-nut material combination, nickel-magnesium gives maximum efficiency as compared to other pairs. The efficiency of double start thread is always higher than that of single one for all pairs of considered materials. The number of threads on the nut and the outside diameter provides another alternative for space available for the designer. Steel-phosphorus bronze combinations

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gives the same minimum number of threads on the nut for both starts of single and double threads. However, screw-nut material combination, of steel-copper and, nickel-magnesium give minimum outside diameters of nut for both starts of single and double threads. As the jack screw efficiency can be improved with increasing the helix angle, titanium – nickel gives maximum helix angle values.

5. Recommendations

- The same work can be extended considering different combination of screw and nut pairs material's.
- Further research should be carried out using Acme and Buttress thread type.
- The same work can be carried out for a different design of screw jack for lifting heavy loads in which nut is rotating while the spindle (screw) moves.

5. References

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